

Exploring climate and environmental ethics in research and innovation with European Research Area stakeholders and international partners: a Social Lab pre-registration

Introduction

Research ethics and integrity frameworks constitute vital cornerstones of the European Research Area (ERA). Historically, research ethics guidelines have been primarily developed in the field of biomedical research, aimed at the protection of human participants. They have also been extended to research in social science, humanities, and technology research involving human subjects or requiring the protection of animals. However, it remains difficult for research ethics frameworks to account for climate, biodiversity, and other environmental concerns in the short, medium, and long term.

The European Union-funded project RE4GREEN (Grant Agreement no.: 101131706) aims to contribute to an ERA ethics and integrity framework for research and innovation (R&I) activities that better accounts for climate and environmental research ethics and research integrity concerns. To do so, RE4GREEN will apply a social lab method (Hassan 2014) to assemble and engage diverse stakeholders to reflect on and consider responses to environmental and climate-related issues. In the context of social labs, the project will ascertain the main programmatic priorities of Horizon Europe pillar 2, focused on social and environmental challenges. Each social lab will cover – in a general way, noting feasibility limits of a representative sample – a different topic area associated with Horizon Europe clusters (e.g., climate, energy, mobility, digital, industry, space, etc.). Coverage will entail: desk-based research on programmatic goals and instruments; interviews with stakeholders from across disciplines, geography, and sector in the ERA; and a set of four participatory workshops designed to promote reflection and response to climate and environmental research ethics and integrity issues.

In addition, and in recognition of the global nature of climate and environmental ethics issues, project partners in South Africa and Japan will each host a lab on a topic similar to one of the ERA labs. These international comparator labs will infuse broader cultural understandings, interpretations, and experiences to the foreground. Doing so is intended to spark additional learning and creative consideration of responses to climate and environmental ethics issues suitable for the short, medium, and long term.

As such, the process of the RE4GREEN social labs seeks to answer the research question:

What are environmental ethics, climate ethics, and research ethics and integrity concerns viewed by stakeholders across topics and sectors in the ERA; how do such concerns compare within the ERA and with international partners; and what responses might be created to address such concerns to guide research, technology and innovation?

Specific objectives are to identify ERA and international stakeholders’:

- perspectives on climate and environmental ethics and integrity concerns in research and innovation generally, in Europe and beyond;

- perspectives on climate and environmental ethics and integrity concerns related to Green Transition research and innovation specifically;
- perspectives on responses to these concerns;
- perspectives on the European Commission’s “do no significant harm” principle and how to better operationalize it;
- perspectives on practices of “Environmental Risk Assessment” and how to integrate climate and environmental ethics and integrity concerns into these.

Methods

RE4GREEN will use Social Labs to drive multi-actor, interdisciplinary, cross-sector, and bottom-up engagement on research ethics and integrity for environmental and climate technologies. During the implementation of the Social Labs, interviews and participatory workshops will be conducted about participant understandings of and experiences with the “do no significant harm” principle, issues of research integrity and benefit sharing, social and environmental justice, ecofeminist viewpoints, and construction of environmental risk assessments. The interviews will also support relationship building for recruitment of participants to the Social Labs.

In the first phase of the Social Lab implementation, two virtual workshops will be carried out to understand different perspectives of environmental and climate ethics and integrity issues and gather insights on how these issues come into play in the practice of general R&I activities as well as R&I for the Green Transition. In the second phase of implementation, the eight RE4GREEN Social Labs will focus on addressing environmental and climate ethics and integrity issues in R&I activities for the Green Transition. Specific foci will cover guidelines, training, and recommendations as intervention areas in European R&I policy and practice. Special attention will be paid to the “do no significant harm” principle and environmental risk assessments.

Concept

The Social Labs are about convening participants to identify and co-create responses to environmental ethics, climate ethics, and research ethics and integrity concerns in the context of research and innovation.

Context

We include participants identified as having topical expertise or interest in research and innovation with climate and environmental ethics implications, or research ethics and research integrity experience. For the ERA Social Labs geographical location is bound to participants from the European Continent. For the international labs, geographical location is bound to South Africa and Japan, respectively, with select additional input from South Korea.

Inclusion Criteria

Languages

The working language of the European Research Area Social Labs will be English, with English being one of the official and working languages of the EU institutions. English will also be the working language of the South African Social Lab. Japanese will be the working language of the Japan Social Lab, with results translated into English for analyses.

Topics

We are looking for concepts, topics, and issues that are related to or that represent aspects of environmental ethics, environmental justice, climate ethics, climate justice, research ethics and integrity, sustainability ethics, environmental harm, bias in environmental risk assessment, and multi-species justice. These concepts, topics, and issues are considered in relation to research, innovation, and technology.

Types of record

This study will include literature in the form of EU program documents, academic and policy literatures, civil society studies, and news media; interview summaries from interviews; workshop reports collecting data from the four participatory activities conducted by each Social Lab.

Exclusion Criteria

This study will exclude:

- Participation of stakeholders outside of the ERA, South African, South Korean, and Japanese context.

Recruitment Strategy

Social Labs will each recruit a minimum of 15 participants for interviews and participation in workshops. Recruitment is based on an analysis of stakeholders connected to the topic area, as assessed through desk research of program documents. The alignment, interest, and influence matrix (AIIM) will be used to think through whom might be involved (Shaxson, 2016).

Assessment of methodological quality

No formal assessment of quality will be included in our Social Lab based study.

Collection of Results

Background document study, interview, and workshop results will be collected in individual reports for each Social Lab. Such “Social Lab Reports” will follow a similar structure to enable subsequent cross-lab comparison.

All members of the Social Lab management team will take part in the data collection process. Pairs of managers from different labs will each independently examine results from their respective other labs. The team will perform qualitative content analysis using the coding matrix developed by Lenzi et al. (2024). This coding matrix will contain definitions,

conceptualizations, and substantial usage of environmental ethics, environmental justice, climate ethics, climate justice, research ethics and integrity, sustainability ethics, environmental harm, and bias in environmental risk assessment.

Lab reports will be distributed for two people to read and code independently using this matrix, with any disagreements resolved in consensus meetings of the project team.

Contribution of WP partners

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Expected Outputs

The expected outputs of this study will be: 1) this Social Lab study protocol; 2) Social Lab Methodology documentation (Deliverable 2.1, January 2027); 3) A Social Lab report on the results of interviews and the first two workshops (Deliverable 2.2, May 2025); 4) A Social Lab report on the second two workshops (Deliverable 2.3, December 2025); 5) A manuscript for peer review publication on European Research Area and international participant perspectives on climate and environmental ethics issues and responses in R&I governance and practice (Deliverable 2.4, April 2026).

Funding Declaration and Competing Interests

This review is funded by Horizon Europe under grant agreement no. 101131706. The review team declares that there are no competing interests.

Ethics Review and Registration

The interviews and Social Lab participation conducted in this study have received ethics review and clearance by respective universities, including:

WP Institutional Partner	Ethical Clearance Number
Austrian Institute of Technology	Following University of Bonn
Autonomous University of Barcelona	CEEAH 6935
University of Cape Town	SCI/00726/2024
University of Bonn	2024-129-BO
Aarhus University	BSS-2024-098-L
European Association of Research Managers and Administrators	Following University of Bonn
European Citizen Science Association	Following University of Bonn
University of Tokyo	Following the University of Tokyo

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